

Transition Metal catalysed Reactions of Organomercurials. II. Palladium-catalysed Carbonylation Reactions

P. G. MORE*, B. J. DESAI and T. N. POWAR

Shivraj College of Science, Gadhinglaj-416 502

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Organomercurials are rarely used in organic synthesis, as compared to Grignard reagents, because of their low reactivity. However, organomercurials have attracted the attention of researchers because of their commercial availability and stability towards air, water and alcohol. They undergo trans-metallation reactions with a number of transition metal salts and this facility has expanded their synthetic potential. The low reactivity of organomercurials can be easily overcome by transition metal catalysis and nucleophilic catalysis reactions. The literature reveals usefulness of organomercurials in organic synthesis¹.

We have reported earlier the palladium catalysed acyldemetallation and cross-coupling reactions of organomercurials which provide mild, selective and general methods for the synthesis of unsymmetrical ketones and arylated heterocycles or biheterocyclic compounds respectively. These reactions proceed selectively in the presence of a nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion)^{2,3}.

The palladium catalysed carbonylation of organotin and organomercurials in the presence of aryl halides, is another route to the unsymmetrical ketones^{3,4}. In the present communication we describe the synthesis of unsymmetrical ketones by the palladium catalysed carbonylation of

(1)

Alk HgI-ArI system in the presence of a nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion) (Reaction 1).

Results and Discussion

The reaction proceeds with best selectivity in HMPA, in the presence of palladium catalyst, PdCl₂(MeCN)₂ (1 mol %) and iodide ion (Bu₄NI, 4 equiv.) under 1 atmosphere of CO at room temperature to get a high yield of unsymmetrical ketone. The results are summarised in (Table 1).

TABLE I-CARBONYLATION REACTIONS OF ArI WITH AlkHgI

Sl no.	Ar	Alk	Time h	Yield* %
1.	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	6	88 (83)
2.	<i>p</i> -I-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	5.5	88 (83)
3.	<i>p</i> -MeO-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	7	88 (80)
4.	<i>p</i> -Me-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	8	79 (75)
5.	<i>p</i> -OHC-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	8	79 (75)
6.	2-C ₅ H ₄ N	CH ₃	7	81 (78)
7.	2-C ₄ H ₃ S	CH ₃	7	83 (79)

*Yield determined by tlc and uv spectroscopy; isolated yield in parenthesis.

Scheme 1

The catalytic cycle of the reaction is depicted in Scheme 1.

The catalytic cycle of the reaction consists of a carbonylation process (A) and a cross-coupling process (B). We found that a large excess of nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion) accelerates the carbonylation process⁴. The carbonylation presumably involves a sequence of oxidative addition, insertion of carbon monoxide, transmetalation and reductive elimination steps. Aryl iodide (ArI) oxidatively adds to Pd⁰ to give ArPdI complex, which further undergoes insertion of carbon monoxide to give ArCOPdI complex. ArCOPdI undergoes transmetalation with AlkHgI to give ArCOPdAlk complex. ArCOPdAlk reductively eliminates unsymmetrical ketone ArCOAlk with the recovery of Pd⁰.

Iodide ion plays an important role in the reaction. It forms an anionic complex with Pd⁰, (Pd⁰I⁻), which reacts quickly with aryl halide in the oxidative addition step⁴. Because of the presence of a large excess of iodide ion, the reaction proceeds without the formation of palladium black.

Experimental

The palladium complex, organomercurials (Alk-HgI) and aryl halides were prepared in the laboratory by using the standard procedures. HMPA was purified and distilled before use. Bu₄NI was

of A.R. grade. The yields of the products were determined by tlc on Silufol-254 and uv spectroscopy. The products were isolated by tlc on silica gel and identified with the help of ir, nmr and mass spectra.

Carbonylation : A mixture of HMPA (2.5 ml), aryl halide (0.5 mmol), Bu₄NI (2 mmol) and Alk HgI (0.55 mmol) was stirred under atmosphere of CO till it became saturated with CO. The palladium complex, PdCl₂(MeCN)₂ (0.005 mmol) (1 mol%) was then added with stirring under CO. The quantitative yield of the ketone was tested by tlc and uv spectroscopy. After the completion of the reaction, the mixture was diluted with water (10 ml) and extracted with ether (3 × 5 ml). The ether solutions were combined and washed with aqueous NaI (2 × 5 ml) to remove traces of Hg salt, dried over MgSO₄ and evaporated to get the ketone.

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